

Supplementary Materials to the article ”Citizen ditching cars: How do assessments of SDG interactions predict a modal shift towards low-carbon urban transport choices?”

Appendix A. Emissions in Switzerland, by sector

Table A1. Green-house gases (carbon dioxide (CO₂), methane (CH₄), nitrous oxide (N₂O) and fluorinated gasses (F-Gas)) in million tonnes of CO₂-equivalent, in Switzerland, 2021, by sector and energy sub-sector. Data source: Climate Watch (2024)

Sector	Sub-sector	2021
Energy:	Transportation	15.02
	Buildings	12.11
	Manufacturing and construction	4.88
	Electricity and heat	3.1
	Other fuel combustion	0.63
	Fugitive emissions	0.24
Agriculture		5.47
Industrial processes		3.53
Bunker fuels		2.34
Waste		0.75
Land-use change and forestry		-1.73

Appendix B. Ordinal variables**Table B1.** Ordinal categories

Variable category	Levels
Urban zone	"City center" "Principal core" "Secondary core" "Urban ring"
Age	"18 to 34 years old" "35 to 54 years old" "55 to 79 years old"
Frequency	"Never" "A few days a year" "A few days a month" "1 to 3 days a week" "At least 4 days a week"
Agreement	"Strongly disagree" "Disagree" "Agree" "Strongly agree"

The asterisks * at the *Interaction* and *Income* variable categories in Table B2 below indicate that two ambiguous, non-ordinal sub-categories were removed from the statistical analysis, which was characterized by several ordinal categorical variables. In the survey, the *Interaction* category of variables initially entailed the answer options "It doesn't make sense" and "I don't know". Similarly, the *Income* range variable initially entailed the answer options "Don't know" and "Prefer not to say".

Table B2. Ordinal categories (continued from Table B1)

Variable category	Levels
Interaction*	"Very negative" "Negative" "No impact" "Positive" "Very positive"
Income*	"4,000 CHF or less" "4,001 - 8,000 CHF" "8,001 - 12,000 CHF" "More than 12,000 CHF"
Education	"Without post-compulsory education" "Upper-secondary level" "Tertiary level"
Climate-friendly behavior	"0 = big emitter" "1" "2" "3 = mid-way efforts" "4" "5" "6 = climate-friendly behavior"

Appendix C. Key reporting points from the Bayesian analysis

In the following tables, we briefly report on key points from our Bayesian analysis by specifying where they are addressed in the main article. We include further details on these points in case they were missing from the main article. The structure follows the checklist provided by the Bayesian Analysis Reporting Guideline (BARG) from Kruschke (2021).

Table C1. BARG reporting

Preamble	
A. Why Bayesian	Subsection 2.3 (Variables in causal model)
B. Goals of analysis	Section 1 (Introduction)
Step 1. Explain the model	
A. Data variables	Figure 2 and Subsubsection 2.3.1 (Observed variables)
B. Likelihood function and parameters	Equations and multi-level β parameters are described in Subsection 2.4 (Statistical tests)
C. Prior distribution	Default prior distribution
D. Formal specification	Subsection 2.4 (Statistical tests) and R scripts available as replication files (Pham-Truffert and Angst 2025)
E. Prior predictor check	See Figures C1, C2, C3 and C4
Step 2. Report details of the computation	
A. Software	Subsection 2.4 (Statistical tests)
B. MCMC chain convergence	Subsection 2.4 (Statistical tests)
C. MCMC chain resolution	Subsection 2.4 (Statistical tests)
D. If not MCMC	Not applicable
Step 3. Describe the posterior distribution	
A. Posterior predictive check	See Figures C1, C2, C3 and C4
B. Summarize posterior of variables	See Figures C5, C6, C7 and C8 and Table C2
C. BF and posterior model probabilities	Not applicable
Step 4. Report decisions (if any) and their criteria	
A. – E.	Not applicable
Step 5. Report sensitivity analysis	
A. – E.	Not applicable
6) Make it reproducible	
A. – H.	See Pham-Truffert and Angst (2025)

Figure C1. Posterior and prior predictive checks for model M1

Figure C2. Posterior and prior predictive checks for model M2

Figure C3. Posterior and prior predictive checks for model M3.a

Figure C4. Posterior and prior predictive checks for model M3.b

Figure C5. Posterior distribution for model M1

Figure C6. Posterior distribution for model M2

Figure C7. Posterior distribution for model M3.a

Figure C8. Posterior distribution for model M3.b

Table C2. Model summary

	(M1)	(M2)	(M3.a)	(M3.b)
CDF[1]	1.04 [0.42, 1.72]	1.63 [0.95, 2.74]	1.10 [0.60, 1.62]	-1.06 [-1.78, 0.12]
CDF[2]	1.34 [0.73, 2.03]	2.22 [1.55, 3.34]	1.51 [1.01, 2.03]	0.11 [-0.60, 1.28]
CDF[3]	1.92 [1.30, 2.61]	2.91 [2.22, 4.03]	2.21 [1.69, 2.74]	1.00 [0.28, 2.18]
CDF[4]	2.77 [2.15, 3.47]	3.73 [3.02, 4.87]	3.13 [2.61, 3.66]	1.50 [0.78, 2.69]
$\beta_{gender_{\{male\}}}$	0.25 [0.06, 0.43]	0.12 [-0.07, 0.30]	0.23 [0.05, 0.41]	-0.18 [-0.37, 0.00]
$\beta_{gender_{\{other\}}}$	-3.94 [-11.28, -0.20]	-3.01 [-11.04, 1.13]	-0.25 [-1.95, 1.42]	3.64 [-0.05, 11.14]
$\beta_{gender_{\{prefer_not_to_answer\}}}$	1.07 [-0.91, 3.03]	-0.19 [-2.05, 1.69]	0.16 [-1.86, 2.15]	-2.18 [-4.25, -0.09]
$\beta_{mode_interaction(car_access_climate)_{\{monotonic_ordered\}}}$	0.17 [0.10, 0.26]			
$\beta_{mode_objective(car_accessibility)_{\{monotonic_ordered\}}}$	0.47 [0.31, 0.66]			
$\beta_{climate_friendly_behaviour_{\{monotonic_ordered\}}}$	-0.07 [-0.14, -0.02]	0.10 [0.03, 0.18]	-0.08 [-0.14, -0.02]	0.09 [0.03, 0.15]
$\beta_{urban_zone_{\{monotonic_ordered\}}}$	0.25 [0.16, 0.33]	-0.05 [-0.12, 0.03]	0.26 [0.18, 0.35]	-0.25 [-0.34, -0.17]
$\beta_{income_{\{monotonic_ordered\}}}$	0.29 [0.17, 0.40]	0.09 [0.00, 0.18]	0.05 [-0.06, 0.18]	-0.16 [-0.27, -0.06]
$\beta_{age_{\{monotonic_ordered\}}}$	0.05 [-0.06, 0.16]	-0.02 [-0.14, 0.11]	-0.08 [-0.20, 0.04]	-0.44 [-0.55, -0.32]
$\beta_{mode_interaction(bike_safety_climate)_{\{monotonic_ordered\}}}$		0.23 [0.08, 0.51]		
$\beta_{mode_objective(bike_safety)_{\{monotonic_ordered\}}}$		0.73 [0.61, 0.85]		
$\beta_{mode_interaction(car_affordability_climate)_{\{monotonic_ordered\}}}$			0.15 [0.08, 0.23]	
$\beta_{mode_objective(car_affordability)_{\{monotonic_ordered\}}}$			0.82 [0.67, 0.98]	
$\beta_{mode_interaction(pt_affordability_climate)_{\{monotonic_ordered\}}}$				0.13 [0.02, 0.43]
$\beta_{mode_objective(pt_affordability)_{\{monotonic_ordered\}}}$				0.62 [0.45, 0.80]
Num.Obs.	583	614	595	610
R2	0.312	0.352	0.479	0.332
ELPD	-774.6	-835.6	-738.5	-789.0
ELPD s.e.	16.6	17.6	18.3	16.6
LOOIC	1549.3	1671.2	1476.9	1577.9
LOOIC s.e.	33.1	35.1	36.6	33.3
WAIC	1548.7	1670.3	1476.2	1577.4

References

- Climate Watch (2024). *Washington, DC: World Resources Institute. Available online at: URL: <https://www.climatewatchdata.org>.*
- Kruschke, John K. (2021). “Bayesian Analysis Reporting Guidelines”. en. In: *Nature Human Behaviour* 5.10. Publisher: Nature Publishing Group, pp. 1282–1291. ISSN: 2397-3374. DOI: [10.1038/s41562-021-01177-7](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41562-021-01177-7).
- Pham-Truffert, Myriam and Mario Angst (2025). “Replication files for ”Citizens ditching cars: How do assessments of SDG interactions predict a modal shift towards low-carbon urban transport choices?” by Myriam Pham-Truffert, Mario Angst, Thomas Breu and Maria J. Santos (2025)”. In: Zenodo. URL: <https://zenodo.org/records/14900322>.